
What Is Wrong with Economic Sanctions: Efforts To Evaluate The Moral Dimensions Of Economics Sanctions

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine whether the imposition of economic sanction has relationship to morality and ethics. Sanctions have become a significant powerful tool of foreign policy since WWI. It is less costly as compare to war or military action and can be effectively utilised in a more flexible and targeted manner. This study investigates under what circumstances 'economic sanctions are morally wrong and how economic sanctions impacts on civilian population. Two case studies of economic sanctions will be discussed in this study: Iran and Myanmar. The researcher finds deleterious effects of economic sanctions in most cases and their usual victims are innocent citizens of the target country.

This paper will focus on moral dimensions of Economics Sanction, their significance in the foreign policy of countries. The main purpose of this paper is to evaluate the impact of economic sanctions on civilian population.

Keywords: Economic Sanctions, moral dimension of economic sanctions, Myanmar and Iran

Introduction

Sanctions are explained as an actions imposed by one or more countries against one or more in order to achieve certain target or goals. The economic restrictions imposed by one regime or group of regimes on another for a range of reasons. Economic sanctions can include arms sanctions, freezing of assets, partial or permanent travel ban for government or military officials and other financial penalties of the targeted regime (Anon., 2005).

The main aim behind sanctions is to influences on the policies and procedures of the targeted regime in power, individual or groups of people, which the sanctioner ‘’believes best for that regime. There are different reasons behind coercive economic sanctions, but immensely depending upon the situations. Economics sanctions may also be imposed to ensure that that weapons of mass distractions do not reach into the wrong hands, or to support terrorist activities. The most frequently applied measures are as follows:

- Restrictions on exporting or delivering of arms, weapons and financing, technical assistance and training.
- Embargo on exporting equipment or tools that might be used for internal repression.
- Financial sanctions on individuals or group of people in government, regulatory bodies and associated businesses, or terrorist groups and individuals associated with those groups,
- Travel restrictions on specific individuals, group of people and their families,
- Embargo on imports or delivering of goods

Since the devastating effect of World War I (1914-1918) economic sanctions have been used as a tool for counterinsurgency or any kind of conflicts between countries. The main purpose of this paper is to evaluate the moral dimensions of economics sanction and to give judgment to their effectiveness and influence. The impact of moral and ethical challenges of economic sanctions has been the main topics of many discussions. Comparing to use military action, economic and political sanctions have become a very strong instrument of international foreign policy

Table 1: Historical background of economic sanctions from (1914-2000)

	1914- 1949	1950- 1959	1960- 1969	1970- 1979	1980- 1989	1990- 1999
Non-U.S.	11	6	7	9	7	18
Other & U.S.	4	4	4	3	8	30
Unilateral U.S	4	3	10	26	13	14
Total	19	13	21	38	28	62
Source: Centre for global development and Institute for International economics, US.						

Literature Review:

This paper builds on the literature on economic sanctions and on the literature of moral dimension and ethical challenges. Several studies such as Hoskins and Nutts (1997),

Garfield and Gibbons (1999) and Garfield (1999) describe that economic sanctions should be used, but only those which will not have criminalizing effects, such as restrictions on import and exports of goods and other prohibited acts. For them, smart sanctions such as freezing of leaders foreign assets and political restrictions are likely to have very few criminalizing penalties, and are therefore better for accomplishing the goal/s.

The concept of coercive economic sanctions are also subject to various definitional debates, Specifically, this study focuses that because economic sanctions mostly affect poor citizens in the affected country, so I will utilizes the definition of Hufbauer, Gary and Kimbrelly (2007) to include coercive economic measures that “ are deliberately applied to prevent, amend, or modify a state or group’s political, military, or economic and political behavior that the sanctioner believes disproportionate” Sometimes, regimes implement unilateral sanctions as a tool when they feel helpless in order to implement their influence upon others. says Peksen, P and Drury (2014).

Peksen (2009) claim that effects of economic sanctions are penalties imposed against another country in order to force that country to change its policies, by inflicting economic losses. Debating on economic sanctions are an international foreign policy tool, Peksen (2009) says that success of sanctions depends on how many regimes are involved in imposing sanctions. As Peksen says, sanctions usually affect normal inhabitants of target

country without achieving required goals. Lektzian D, and Souva (2007) argue that economic sanctions harm only poor inhabitants of countries. Knowing this fact, we can say that coercive economic sanctions are really inept. They affect those innocent and poor people that are not real goal of economic sanctions. But sanction imposing countries do not bother about innocent people. They only focus on the outcome of their political objectives.

There are many aspects in sanctions that they tend to be the most significantly influence or even change the strategies of a regime, punish or penalize a nation because of its policies or behaviour. In summary, the motives and intentions of the sanctions can be presented as follows:

- The desire to influence the policies, behaviour or even a change in the government political system of a national and international policies
- Create instability by empowering government's opposition, mostly in an attempt to change in political system of the nation
- Promoting human rights justice, counter-terrorism and development of arms and weapons. (Alikhani, 2001)
- This paper also draws from studies on the elements of economic sanctions such as Currie and Stabile (2003) explore that increased usage of economic sanctions are

somehow reasonable because it is better than through military acts or war situation. This reason is very strong, but on the other hand, Bapat and Morgan (2009) have focused on the higher economic power and better political situation in terms of their success and failures however, Dizaji and Van Bergeijk (2013) determine that "to impose more efficient powerful sanctions on poor countries, this indicates that economic sanctions always perform only the rich countries and they are mainly toward innocent and ordinary inhabitant of the countries".

What are the Economic Sanctions?

- Economic sanctions used as an instrument where one country impose sanctions on another country. Economic sanctions imposed directly and indirectly, the direct sanctions mainly focused on target area, whereas indirect sanctions mainly impact departments, institutions, employment and ultimately individual nutrition Shehabaldin and Laughlin Jr (1999)
- Dizaji and Van Bergeijk (2013) find that the implementation of economic sanctions jeopardies social, political and civil rights of the inhabitants, thereby resulting in weakening democratic liberty.
- The sanctions imposing countries often have hidden agenda and under the policy of removing the ruling government and they also target people they do not like or people considered to be dangerous (killings of Iran's famous nuclear scientists).

Hoskins and Nutt (1997) describe three moral dimensions of economic sanctions that impact attainment of economic sanctions: sanctions that express interest, institutions and punishment. Sanctions for expressing interest do not mainly focused on making changes in domestic or foreign polices of other nations.

□ Economic sanctions were very effective during 1930s and 1940s. But after expansions in world economy and rise in usage of unilateral sanction, usefulness of those sanctions is massively diminished. In Today’s era economies sanctions are very linked and they deeply depend on worldwide trade.

□ Jeffrey, Gary and Hufbauer (2007) find economic sanctions are tools for foreign policy showing country’s sentiments regarding some conditions and tools for international political changes. Countries also use economic and political sanctions as a tool for controlling countries that are fail to comply national and international human rights of their citizens, or they have some potential to become danger to the rest of the world

Effect of economic sanctions on innocent citizens

Economic sanctions most of the time harm poor and innocent people of targeted regimes, because sanction imposing countries know very well that

the easiest way to achieve their motives is to turn people against their government. Cuba is a clear example that sanctions affected more innocent people than Cuban military or government officials.

Shehabaldin and Laughlin Jr (1999) “Economic sanctions is a political strategy of turning the screws or “mounting pressure” gives the target regimes time to adjust by finding substitute traders or potential markets, by building new business strategic alliances, and by mobilizing national estimation in support of its policies.”

Economic sanctions have detrimental effect on local people and innocent citizens of the country. The fundamental aim of economic sanctions is to target rulers of the country in order to change their views and policies. Lowenberg (2007a) suggest that the US sanctions against Cuba added to a fall in nutritious value and growth is diseases. As a result of these various impacts, different sectors of the population may experience varying degrees of income loss under economic sanctions.

Table 2: Security Council sanctions in accordance with Article 41 of the UN Charter (1944-1998) H.J.G. Zandman (Kulesa & Starck, 1998)

Target country	Period	Type of sanctions
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Somalia	1992-	Sanctions on air traffic
South Africa	1977- 1994	Arms sanctions
Haiti	1993-1994	Oil and arms sanctions, freezing of international money transfer and bank-accounts
Yugoslavia	1992-1995	Wide-ranging of economic sanctions, restriction on service-sector business, sports and cultural sanctions, sanctions on air traffic
Rhodesia	1967-1978	Economic sanctions, money transfer sanctions, travel bans and freezing of foreign bank account Arms embargo, restrictions on air traffic, diplomatic
Libya	1992-	sanctions, freezing of foreign bank-accounts, partial embargo
Liberia	1992-	Arms embargo
Angola	1993-	Oil and arms embargo, Oil and arms embargo, ban on air-travel, closure of offices abroad
Iraq	1990	Economic sanctions, ban on air traffic and Oil and armsembargo
Sudan	1996-	Arms sanctions, travel ban for government and military officials, restrictions on air traffic

Although, the expansion of smart sanctions has elucidated many of the political problems that prior efforts at overall sanctions had created. Smart sanctions tested as a useful tool for sanction imposing countries (Weingast and Garrett 1993). According to Schott and Elliott (2007), there were many sanctions imposed in parts at the end of the Cold War as there were during the first 90 years of the twentieth century. For examples United Nations sanctions on Iraq, Cuba, Haiti, and former Yugoslavia in the early 1990s (Thomas Weiss and Larry Minear 1997). It is observed that, in the end, all sanctions generated at least sufficient concessions. Obviously, military force was also used in all cases, but Rogers (1997) claim that economic sanctions played a fundamental supporting role in shaping the outcomes. The history shows that the economic sanctions imposed on Iraq have suffered innocent people, where they were unable to purchase medicines and unable to survive due

to high inflation. This shows how sanctions affect innocent inhabitants. Radcliffe (2010) derived few important conclusions regarding economic sanction that the use of economic sanctions to pressure or influence target countries is of limited relevance while Dizaji and Van Bergeijk (2013) find that the implementation of economic sanctions jeopardies social, political and civil rights of the inhabitants, thereby resulting in weakening democratic liberty. In above sanctions we can clearly see failure rate of sanctions and there is only one case is successful (India's embargo against Nepal's regime) according to Pape (1998). During 1990s, the United Nations Security Council voted for economic sanctions twelve times; However, only two sanctions were enforced from 1945 and 1990, (Lopez and Cortright 2000). Hufbauer, G., Schott, J., Elliott (2007) argue three basic causes for the sanctions imposition: (i) to pressurize regimes to terminate acts that challenge the independence of another country (ii) to protect democracy in the country or to take action against dictator administration (iii) to protect the people of a country from cruel political tyranny and implement human rights. Sanctions are supposed to enforce economic hardship on the country and make the government change its policies

Table 3:

High Punishment and Sanctions Outcomes.				
Year	Coercer	Target	GNP Loss	Outcome
1967	Nigeria	Biafra	15.2	failure
1951	U.K./U.S.	Iran	14.3	failure
1965	U.K./UN	Rhodesia	13.0	failure
1982	U.S./Netherlands	Suriname	7.8	failure
1975	U.S.	Cambodia	6.8	failure
1987	U.S.	Panama	6.0	failure
1982	South Africa	Lesotho	5.1	overdetermined
1989	India	Nepal	4.6	success

Cases of Coercive Economic Sanctions

Iran Economic And Political Sanctions

Iran faced the economic sanctions during U.S- Iran hostage crisis in 1979-81, the sanctions banned all U.S. exports to Iran.

During Iran's post revolutionary years 1979-1989, this period was challenging for the Iran's economy due to conflict with neighboring country Iraq. During 1989-1992 Post-War

reconstructions, Iran was under international pressure due to development and expansion of nuclear program. Whereas in 1993-1995, the Government of United States imposed strong restriction on Iran's economy through Dual Containment and Trade Sanctions.

'Dual Containment and Trade policy was officially introduced by US and officially introduced in 1993. The main purpose of "Dual containment and Trade policy" was to isolate Iran and Iraq from international politics.

However, in 2002 and 2003, UN, European Union and other American Allies (strategic partners) imposed economic sanctions on Iran due to hidden nuclear programme, Iran asserted. The three countries Saudi Arabia, United States and Israel have major concerns on the development of Iran's nuclear program and they threatened Iran with war.

According to the USA, Iran has plans to produce an atomic bomb. In this way the neighboring countries including Turkey, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Syria and some other countries in the region may also feel that in order to balance the power they also need nuclear weapons as well. Iran has openly announced its full support to Palestinians in their fight for independence. This is why Israel sees Iran as its major security threat to the Jewish

state. The rise of nuclear-armed Iran may not just imbalance the power in Middle East but may lead to nuclear proliferation by other regional states. Let say Iran has no negative aim to use nuclear power against Israel or any other neighbor country, but still uncertainly will remain in all the neighboring countries.

The UN enforced sanction including: all exports to Iran, technological equipment and all other kind material that could help Iran for further development of Nuclear Program; a ban of any support to any individual/s that could help in exports of sanction goods to Iran; a ban on exports of all weapons and guns as well as a sanctions on all financial assistance that could be helpful for Iran's Nuclear enrichment program; asset freeze to all individual/s that could be part or support for the development of Nuclear enrichment program ; a travel restrictions on individual/s that could be part or support for the development of Nuclear enrichment program and others.

Since 1987 US stopped importing Iranian oil and has pressured most EU and Non EU countries, including French multinational Oil and Gas Company and Anglo-Dutch oil firm Royal Dutch Shell to stop investing in the country's oil industry

Due to nuclear programme, UN imposed political and economic sanctions against Iran. Since 2005, UN imposed different economic and other sanctions against Iran. The UN sanctions were enforced as follows: first round in 2006, second in 2007, third in 2008 and

fourth in 2010. Those sanctions were enormous and they affected all parts of Iran's economy and its civilian.

Table 4: Iran's exports of Crude Oil and economic sanctions

Source: U.S. Energy Information Administration

Non-UN ban also contained embargo of financial support into Iran's in any project including Oil and Gas sector. European Union and the United States, Spain, Italy, Greece and many other countries focused their ban on all individual/s that are part of Iran's nuclear program as well as ban against major financial institutions in Iran.

The latest sanctions announced by United States Treasury Department against Iran after missile test (03 February, 2017).

The US treasury department also included the list of 12 entities and 13 people facing new sanctions. EU ban imports of oil and petroleum products from Iran; EU frozen all assets of Iran's Central bank; EU and US banned Iran's trade in precious materials included gold, silver and diamonds.

Table 5: European Union trade with Iran

Source: European Commission, DG Trade (2015)

Although EU imposed some strong sanctions on Iran but such restrictions cost equally to EU as well. According to World Bank statistics almost 45% of Iran’s oil is bought by EU countries, and even though Europe believes these ban will affect Iran the most, but in reality it does not have to be the case.

The Effect of the international sanctions on Iran

In contrast, the economic sanctions have detrimental effects on the citizen of Iran. First, in 1979 as a result of hostage dispute, United States froze Iranian government assets, goods

and services embargo, trade and investment ban, oil embargo by the European Union. Second, many multinational corporations

voluntarily left Iranian market and reduced their investment mainly in oil sector. Third, several food, automobile, fuel and electronic suppliers reduced their business with Iran. Forth, the coercive economic sanctions impact on Iran's foreign exchange market. Fifth, the embargo on the Iranian financial institutions, the Iranian currency became devalued and inflation rate increased a lot. Due to sanctions, Iranian oil exports dropped and Iranian regime fail to find out alternative markets. Iran had no choice other than to sell oil by lowering prices. The international sanctions restrict Iranian banking sector to transfer international supplier payments, payment to Iranian subsidiary companies based in international market.

The Impacts of EU and Non EU Sanctions on Iran's Crude Oil

Since 2006 European Union imposed sanctions on Iranian nuclear programmes, Iran is the first country, where European Council enforced sanctions because of their weapons of mass destructions (WMD) concerns. The European Union mainly took initiative of economic sanctions against Iran when United Nations Security Council launched an approach to ban Iran exports with the name of 'Dual Track'. Table 5 shows, when it comes to the imports of crude oil shows how EU countries enormously depend upon on Iran crude. Greece, even having lot of economic issues but they still too much relies on crude oil from Iran. Economic sanctions enforced by many countries of the world, made Iran's payments tougher, and therefore Iran's oil imports from many countries is decreased a lot, even imports from those that did not impose sanctions

Table 6: Iran before and after oil sanctions

IRANIAN OIL EXPORTS: BEFORE AND AFTER SANCTIONS

Iranian Oil Exports by Destination (approximate)
Barrels per day

Source: International Energy Agency (IEA)

Foreign Direct Investment in Iran and effect of economic sanctions There are different meanings of foreign direct investment (FDI) . Transferring of funds, capital or materials from one state to another state in order to utilise the services of a company in the host country in return of Foreign direct investment,

Sanctions on Foreign Direct investment are kind of financial sanctions that may reflect in international relations policies of the countries. There are different phases involved in financial sanctions. In the first phase, the potential sanctioning country begins to negotiate with the target country and reassure it to change its behaviour, policy or policies. The phase two is to inform public about sanctions through public announcements, and third phase is to take into confidence to other countries and International strategic allies, the fourth phase is starting of monetary and non-monetary embargoes. In case of Iran, Most of International companies gave up to invest in Iran due to uncertain political situations. Others companies gave up due to extensive US, Israel and the UN pressure. All above two factors Influenced International investors out of Iran. Without FDI, Iran’s economy suffered a lot.

Table 7: Iran before and after oil sanctions

Source: U.S Energy Information administration, 2012

5. The coercive economic sanctions impact adversely on Iran's Foreign Direct investment. Iran is located in the western Asian region and has got a great strategic position. As shown in table 7, It is obvious that how Foreign direct investment in Iran diminished after the strong political and economical sanctions. Without international economic cooperation it is almost impossible for Iran to have economic development with support of international economic cooperation and development. Therefore, decline in foreign investors have negative effects on Iran's economic situation.

Myanmar Economic And Political Sanctions

Since the beginning of 1990s the political and economical sanctions have been in place in Myanmar. The sanctions were imposed in response to the Myanmar's military violation of human rights. The sanctions have always been debated as to whether they are achieving the desired outcome or if they only exist as a political tool to pressurise the local regime of

the sanctioning countries The Economic Sanctions are effective tool that can be much more utilised by wealthy countries as compare to poor. The multilateral and unilateral sanctions both have ethical impact on the targeted country, particularly when sanctions are enforced over the longer period of time. The only way economic restrictions can be justified is if the sanctioner imposed sanctions as a “symbol of power” in positive and constructive way rather than in negative form. Then perhaps, there is a space for economic sanctions as a means to shape international moral and ethics norms for the better. In this research we can see that economic sanctions found fruitless when examined both ethically and in terms of effectiveness.

UN, US and EU International rules and regulations to impose sanctions 1993-2013

International sanction guideline is very clear that how to impose sanctions. The sanctions must obey human rights law and respect international treaties. Furthermore, the sanctions imposed must always be in accordance to their objectives. The United States criteria for imposing economic and financial sanctions are more detailed and comprehensive. The research shows that United States regimes have implemented much more sanctions as compared to the sanctions imposed by all other countries. United States international sanctions policy is more toward targeted sanctions against countries, which support terrorist activities, deals with weapons of mass destruction, to violate human and civil

rights, to abuse of political and judicial system of country. The United States impose multilateral financial and economic sanctions with other strategic allies or countries, yet most of the time United States imposition of sanctions are undertaken on a unilateral basis. Myanmar is the best example where United States imposed sanctions without the approval of UN Security Council Sanctions Committee.

EU trade with Myanmar

Source: European commission- directorate general for trade

The United States imposed restriction on Myanmar during 1993. The sanctions included revocation of all licenses, import and exports of defense equipment, or defense services by United States manufacturers. The sanctions restricted the exporting of arms licenses, technical assistance arms and weapons, technical data sharing and military trade agreements of any type/types subject to the Arms Export Control Act.

Since 1993, the US exports control regulatory authority stated clearly that re-export controls apply to all US supplied military components. Thus, any US manufacturing good exported further into Myanmar would require a United States export license. US sanctions include an embargo on all imports from Myanmar, ban on international financial

transactions, and an asset freeze on certain named Burmese individuals, group of people and organizations. However, EU imposed sanctions on imports related income to the military Junta.

As per US treasury department reports that billions of worth of financial transactions have been blocked since the embargo of financial services to Myanmar. Furthermore, there is a sanction on new investment in Myanmar, restriction on arms and weapons sales, restrictions on humanitarian assistance. US sanctions play an important role at foreign policy intervention at national affairs of Myanmar. The main objective behind US policy is to isolate government of Myanmar in hopes that when the pressure level will rises very high, the Burman people will rise up and protest against their government. In 2006, US president signed legislation extended the financial sanctions against Myanmar for another year. In 2007, the United States imposed sanctions on Myanmar by freezing assets in the United States of military officials and key government members. In case of unilateral sanctions on goods, the US position was not strong as US was not one of the largest goods supplier and exporters of the sanctioning goods. Due to inflation and other economics

issues, the US economic position has been decreased and its overall production and consumption capacity as they used to and have now decreased upto 25%.

Different approaches to sanctions against Myanmar

In response to human rights violations, the United States, European Union and United Nation slapped Myanmar with sanctions. Initially, the US imposed broad sanctions in order to isolate Myanmar as a way of pushing the military government and people of Myanmar towards a revolution. European Union imposed targeted sanctions to persuade the Burmese military government as directly as possible. Myanmar became a member of the United Nations in 1948, however United Nation, not through sanctions, but with productive engagement, is the only one conducting a negotiation with Myanmar through Special Envoy Ibrahim Gambari. Since all three UN, EU and US have different approaches to how to solve the problem; it is difficult to extract any result. The Burmese regime is using the different strategies to its advantage by blaming the sanctions for not being able to make and improvement in their development towards democracy. So, the lack of coordination between the three key stakeholders UN, EU and US have self-centered effects and is used by the military regime to its advantage.

Sanctions against Myanmar and sanctions theory

The sanctions theory of economics has long sought to explain why economic sanctions become fail, the sanction theory based on two phases. First phase, the target country must agree to an important part of the coercer's demands. Second phase, sanctions must be the primary reason for the target's change of behavior. These two phases aim to alter all other explanations for change of conduct and behavior. Currently, there are number of economic sanction approaches in use and it is therefore difficult to define whether the sanctions are successful or not. Milikovic claims that sanctions vary vastly in terms of their sources, targets, drives, types, scope, effects, and influence as policy instruments.

However, in order to extract desirable results from sanctions both economic and financial sanctions need to be in place in addition to the absence of support from third party or parties. In Myanmar's case, both economic and financial sanctions have been imposed but third party support is still there. The sanctioning regimes always take advantage of its large economy than the receiving regime's economy. Sanctions, which are intended to change

the policies and behavior of a target country, are very difficult to design and implement. Thus, the target regime adjusts by finding substitute suppliers on the market and by building new strategic alliances.

Moral dimensions of direct and Indirect of economic Sanctions

Indirect sanctions also have an impact same as direct sanctions, but also supporting sectors will effect, unemployment is one of the key area to check economic stability of the country, The sanctions affect employment in the targeted country and leads to reduced per capita income on the whole. The purchasing power also decreases due to lack to income, thus falling the people's' living standards, ultimately forcing them into a state of lack of nutritional facilities mainly emphasises on theoretical information to find out how resources are effectively utilised, swapped or modified under sanctions. The theoretical data refers to situations or information that can only partially be listed and therefore must be assessed as to what effect it may have.

The time frame between the imposition of the financial/economic sanction and the actual implementation affects several areas such as the utilities, investments and transportation available in the target regime

Unemployment in Myanmar is also one of the big causes due to sanctions, seen in box 2 in figure 8. Due to sanctions foreign investors hesitate to bring their investment in Myanmar, especially multinational companies those are using dollar as an international currency for domestic and international payments. Textile Industry suffers due to very strict United States sanctions on import/export and investment. The result has been people unemployed

in Textile industry as well as other related industries. People with good education and extensive experiences either leave the country or suffer from lack of motivation. The only option left with the people and that is to join army, which has been the only and best way of development.

Overall high level of corruption has weakened chances for educated and skilled people to find good jobs. The result has made a bad impact on the humanitarian development due to the lack of proper information and expertise in the overall country. When the rate of unemployment sector is increasing the overall per capita income for every family drops, see box 3 figure 8. The impact of economic sanctions has been shifted to the society in several areas. The affected government has only choice to meet the needs of country by printing as much as notes, however which is not a good solution.

Figure 8: Moral Dimensions of direct and target Sanctions

The bitter outcome, as shown in box 4 in figure 8, is a lack of food for many workers. Targeted business and commerce ban lead those industries to decrease local funds for society and government functions, including health, safety and social services.

The result in box 5 in figure 8, focuses on nutritional affects on the overall society. Due to economic sanctions, according to an estimate around one third of the children suffered from it. Most of the families are struggling in order to provide basic nutritional facilities to their

family members and rely mostly on basic food commodities. These outcomes are difficult to calculate before imposing sanctions or ban on any regime.

Conclusion

The aim of this paper is to investigate the efforts to evaluate the moral dimensions of economics sanctions.

In order to achieve political and economic goals, countries utilise sanctions as a key tool to fulfil their motives. I found in my research work that the concept of economic sanctions is not new; Economic sanctions have been used since World War I and there is a great shift from traditional sanctions to targeted sanctions. This research focuses to a growing literature that the concepts of economic sanctions have been increased from last few decades. The most famous sanctions were against Myanmar, Iran, Cuba and Zimbabwe. During my research study I found economic sanctions are generally inefficient, in many

research studies that have been investigated more than 160 economic sanctions found that economic sanctions establish success rate in less than 5% of all cases investigated. Apart from highlighting the impact of economic sanctions, this paper also emphasizes that the moral dimension of economic sanctions have inadvertent

costs for the local inhabitant and may affect the ordinary public more than the sanctioned country's leadership. Therefore, sanctioner country needs to be more careful of their actions having influences that are unintended or unethically harmful. On the other hand, the sanctioned country should be notified about the impact and consequences of sanctions. So it can be concluded that economic sanctions are morally wrong in achieving their desired goals.

It is obvious that imposition of coercive economic sanctions on oil and utilities stuff will harm innocents the most.

The economic consequences of oil restriction are the cause of inflation and ultimately rise in the prices of all commodities. This inflation will affect purchasing power of ordinary citizens of a country. All sanctions should be properly planned in order to avoid harming on poor and innocent citizens. This study finds that almost all direct, indirect, economic and political sanctions affected innocent citizens in every country where they were imposed.

In this study, two examples of economic sanctions are taken to find 'Efforts to evaluate the moral dimensions of Economics Sanction'. Economic sanctions imposed against Iran and Myanmar.

After reviewing of Iran's sanctions it can be concluded that the impact of sanctions are more severe on the target country when sanctions span has longer duration. The economic sanctions imposed against Iran are partially effective due to decline Iran's nuclear program, but not fully successful in a way that they could not stop it totally.

This study also found that the imposition of unilateral or multilateral sanctions have unintentional consequences may affect the innocent people more than the sanctioned state's leaders. Thus, sanctioner needs to be made conscious of their actions having good or bad effects that are unintentional or unfairly harmful. It is expected that imposition of economic and political sanctions on oil and goods will shake innocents the most. On the other hand, the target regimes should be admonished about the direct and indirect impact of sanctions on the innocent people of the country. While I find evidences in my study that economic and financial embargos produce the greatest loss to the local community in decreasing

business and commerce, unemployment in the country, decrease in per capita income and ultimately decrease in worker nutritional level.

In case of Myanmar, the research work shows that very rarely does any economic sanction solely fulfill the actual target without affecting the innocent civilian of the target country, whether it is trade and commerce, monetary sanctions, partial or targeted sanctions. Due to economic sanctions, several businesses have closed and thousands of people became jobless. The tourism industry revenue has reduced enormously. Consequently, the low wage rate condition, which has developed due to the high competition in employment sector, causes incomes to decrease and results in a state of undernourishment of the innocent people.

Sanctioning countries should fully understand through their aims and objectives before taking any final step to implement sanctions on any target country. The decision makers in the sender regime should be confident that their aims and objectives are within their reach, that they can deploy sufficient economic pressure to lead command the attention of the target regime.

Although economic and political sanctions may be the only option in some of the situations where it is diplomatically necessary to “do something,” not just any other kind restriction or sanction will do: The sanction chosen must be fitting to the conditions. Sanctioner usually has multiple aims and objective, when they impose coercive sanctions. Wise leaders always carefully examine the ‘moral dimensions’ before taking a final decision to deploy any sanctions

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